

Public Sector & Nature-based Solution (NbS) Investment: Drivers, hurdles and ideas to overcome them

About this brief

This brief presents insights of the Invest4Nature (I4N) **public sector interviews on barriers and drivers of NbS investment**, and the role of different governance levels in shaping the implementation of NbS projects.

It highlights:

- ▶ Key drivers influencing NbS investments
- ▶ Main barriers to NbS finance
- ▶ Recommendations for enhancing public sector engagement and support for NbS initiatives

For more details and sources, read Chapter 4 of the Invest4Nature report:

Markets, Financing and Incentives for Nature-based Solutions (Deliverable 3.3).

➤ [Read the full report](#)

Context

Ecosystem services and nature restoration represent immense future economic value that can be delivered by Nature-based Solutions (NbS). They are cost-effective interventions that provide environmental, social, and economic benefits while strengthening climate and community resilience. Examples include restoring wetlands to reduce flooding, planting trees to improve air quality, and creating urban green spaces to enhance community well-being.

Despite these wide-ranging benefits, the economic value of NbS remains under-recognized, limiting incentives for investment. Current investment levels are insufficient to meet the financial requirements needed to limit global warming to 1.5°C by 2050 and to halt biodiversity loss, underscoring the urgency of scaling up NbS financing (United Nations Environment Programme, 2022).

The interviews with public sector representatives provided valuable insights into their real-life experiences with NbS financing and implementation. These discussions revealed both the key drivers and main challenges influencing public sector investments in NbS. They also highlighted several opportunities on how to overcome financial and institutional barriers to enhancing public sector investment in NbS.

Consistent with previous research, all public sector interviewees emphasized that public financing plays the biggest role in NbS financing. EU legislation is creating new opportunities, especially through public-private partnerships, that could significantly boost investment in NbS.

Digital version: Lienhart, L. et al. (2026) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18399633>

Key Drivers of NbS finance

In short

- ▶ **Governance** as accelerator for paradigm shift: laws, regulations and funding
- ▶ **Resilience management** (stormwater management; urban heat management etc.)
- ▶ **Quality of life, health and wellbeing**
- ▶ **City image, best-practice examples and tourism**

Governance as a driving force

EU regulations, as well as local and regional legislation play a major role in the implementation of NbS projects, because they promote a **paradigm shift** towards a higher awareness for the importance of ecosystem services that NbS can deliver to society. Especially **laws and policies targeting conservation and pro-motion of biodiversity** were re-garded a huge driver. Regarding the local scale, authorities have the possibility to safeguard existing green spaces, counteract land sealing as well as prescribe certain quantities and types of greenery in the building sector through urban planning and building regulations.

Frequency of NbS drivers emerged from public sector interviews.

Livability, wellbeing and health

Quality of life, the visual appearance of the city, wellbeing and health benefits for residents, are highly relevant for public investment decisions - and they serve as a key argument for investing in NbS such as urban greening. From an economic perspective, NbS can increase building value, enhance city's image and attractiveness for tourism, and generate cost savings in the health sector. In this context, best-practice examples from neighboring municipalities can be a huge driver.

Risen awareness due to climate change

In recent years, rising awareness of climate change has become a key driver for NbS. **Increasing floods, heatwaves, and declining water levels** have heightened public and political recognition of the need for action. NbS are increasingly valued for their **multifunctionality**, offering environmental, social, and health benefits that many cities now acknowledge. However, smaller municipalities remain less familiar with relevant guidelines, despite overall growth in national awareness and policy support.

Key Barriers for NbS finance

In short

- ▶ **Uncertainty** regarding regulatory gaps and conflicting legislation
- ▶ **Lacking knowledge and trust** in NbS' effectiveness
- ▶ **Institutional silos** and the need for cooperation between departments
- ▶ **Budget constraints**
- ▶ **Complex funding application**

Governance and regulatory barriers

Public decision-makers highlighted that laws and regulations are sometimes not streamlined, which can hinder the implementation of NbS. Legal gaps or conflicts at the national or local level create uncertainty and pose potential risks for private investors and decision-makers. For example, aligning regulations across different governance levels can reduce conflicts, clarify responsibilities, and make it easier to implement NbS projects. Another frequently experienced challenge is different governmental departments working against each other instead of cooperating.

Capacity barriers

Municipalities often struggle with a lack of capacity. small budgets are often just enough for the bare essentials. NbS investments are often not the first priority. Also maintenance costs can be financial risk factor for municipalities with little experience as they are difficult to estimate and not entailed in most funding programs. Due to its complexity funding application also was noted to pose a hurdle to smaller municipalities.

Most frequent barriers regarding NbS investment based on public sector interviews.

Awareness barriers

A lack of awareness and understanding among decision-makers and the public can create uncertainty around NbS implementation and long-term maintenance. Interviewees particularly emphasized that decision-makers and civil society lack trust in functionality and effectiveness of green solutions, placing more trust in grey solutions. Additionally, municipalities also often lack access to expert knowledge and NbS -experienced staff.

Recommendations

1. Promote awareness and trust

All governance levels should collaborate in **providing comprehensive information** about the effectiveness, financial performance, and general benefits of NbS to generate knowledge, professional expertise, and increased visibility: **Need for cross-sectoral cooperation** between governmental departments to identify and promote the multi-fold benefits of NbS across sectors.

Foster information campaigns targeting the general public and **expert training** for employees of public institutions at national and local levels, which could help authorities to overcome resource shortage of trained personnel and ensure long-term awareness and support.

2. Simplify funding application

In order to ease access for communities to NbS funding, it is necessary to refine the application procedures for funding in order to achieve simpler application process, particularly for EU and national funding schemes. Furthermore, funding schemes that directly target NbS could promote cross-sectoral financing for both implementation and maintenance.

3. Strengthen governance lead

The European Union is already a huge driving force behind the promotion of NbS, providing legislative frameworks, strategic guidance, and funding that primarily support action at the local level. However continued progress needs to be made in streamlining regulations across governance levels regarding NbS as legal gaps or conflicting legislation at national or local level can create uncertainty and hinder local decision-makers to implement NbS.

4. Foster cross-sectoral cooperation and funding

Effective cooperation across multiple governance levels is essential for enabling NbS investment and implementation. The synergies created through coordinated action should be leveraged more strategically. To support this, overarching management authorities for NbS could be established at regional or local levels to coordinate efforts between departments, generating added value. Furthermore, **stronger cooperation with the private sector** should be promoted by **offering incentives** that align with broader EU frameworks, such as corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives and the EU Taxonomy for sustainable activities.

Recommendations

	Simplify NbS funding		Close regulatory gaps	Foster cross-sectional cooperation	Enhance awareness and visibility of NbS	
EU-scale	Simplify the application and approval process for NbS project funding	Introduce funds specifically geared towards NbS measures	Strengthen sustainability laws (with special regard to the building sector)	Strengthening the concept of the circular economy	Maintain or scale up research funding, as it brings knowledge and attention to decision-makers and the public	
National scale	Simplify the application and approval process for NbS project funding				Introduce tax incentives for companies that support public authorities in NbS projects	Enable cross-sectional NbS-staff training for employees of public institutions
Regional/ Local scale	Incentivize cross-sectional cooperation (joint funding)	Examine possibilities to include the maintenance of NbS in funding schemes	Reduce conflicts with older laws/regulations by applying them to NbS	Enhance attractiveness of public-private partnerships (local partnerships, carbon certificates) Leverage synergies of NbS by introduce umbrella management authority that brings various departments and topics together	Cooperate with other publicly influential institutions such as local football clubs for NbS awareness campaigns	

Policy recommendations according to scale based on public sector interviews.

The economics of nature-based solutions

Invest4Nature

Invest4Nature aims to attract investments in one of the key measures of climate change adaptation and risk reduction: **Nature-based Solutions (NbS)**

In Invest4Nature's vision to create flourishing markets for nature-based solutions (NbS), it **aims** to:

- Create thorough understanding of **the economic costs and benefits** of NbS to enable the creation of business models and suitable market conditions for NbS
- Develop a **decision support** tool to enable private & public stakeholders make **informed decisions** on NbS investments
- Create a multi-stakeholder **online marketplace**
- Establish a European NbS **investment community**

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